

Nouns as nominal premodifiers in disciplinary research articles written by Filipino research writers: A cross-investigation

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Nouns as nominal premodifiers (NNPs) are an underexplored area of research in L2 academic research writing. In this paper, I cross-investigated NNPs in published qualitative and quantitative research articles (RAs) written by Filipino research writers (FRWs) in Applied Linguistics (AL), Communication (COM), and Measurement and Evaluation (ME) using Biber et al.'s (2021) noun premodifiers framework, with the aid of Hernandez's (2021) syntactic patterns. Major results revealed that NNPs dominantly co-occurred across disciplinary RA sub-registers, especially in quantitative ME RAs with the highest frequency of use of noun premodifiers. One-way ANOVA between groups with Post hoc Tukey *HSD* yielded no significant difference between noun premodifiers across disciplinary RAs. It was concluded that NNPs are widely significant, compressed, and implicit syntactic features of quantitative and qualitative disciplinary RAs. Regardless of disciplines, FRWs commonly use them to maintain economy of expression and compact packaging of information. Noun premodifiers make quantitative and qualitative disciplinary RAs as specialized sub-registers of academic research writing. Implications for research writing curricula, academic research writing instruction, and academic research journals are discussed.

Keywords: Academic Writing; Compression; Disciplinary Research Articles; Filipino Research Writers; Implicitness; NNPs; Nominal Premodifiers

1. Introduction

Nouns as nominal premodifiers (NNPs) or noun premodifiers are one of the indices of syntactic complexity in academic research writing (Biber & Gray, 2010, 2016; Lu, 2010, 2017), contradicting the notions of elaboration and explicitness in academic written discourse (Hyland, 2007, 2008; Hyland & Tse, 2005; Li & Ge, 2009; Wright, 2008). Unlike other phrasal modifiers, noun premodifiers are compressed and implicit syntactic structures whose 'affordances'—to borrow a term from Salmani Nodoushan (2021b)—enable them to (a) create very dense information packaging and (b) foster embedded and confusing meaning relations (Biber & Gray, 2010, 2016; Biber et al., 1999, 2021; Gray, 2015; Ruan, 2018, Wu et al., 2020). As compressed and implicit

features, they may cause lack of comprehension especially to non-specialist readers (Biber & Gray, 2010, 2016; Ruan, 2018), may occur in complex noun sequences (Biber et al., 1999, 2021; Ruan, 2018), and are extremely frequent phrasal premodifications in academic research writing (Biber & Gray, 2016).

NNPs are adequately studied in L1 academic research writing (e.g., Biber & Gray, 2010, 2016; Biber et al. 1999, 2021; Biber et al., 2011; Halliday, 1993/1996); nevertheless, they are understudied in L2 academic research writing. L2 academic research writing differs from L1 academic research writing in that the former is carried out by L2 English research writers who are either ESL (English as a second language), EFL (English as a foreign language), ELF (English as a lingua franca), or EIL (English as an international language) users-also known as L2 English users. Needless to say, L2 English research writers' use of noun premodifiers has earned little research despite the fact that the number of L2 English users has exceeded the number of L1 English users around the globe (Crystal, 2003, 2008; Jenkins, 2015).

Like other L2 English research writers or L2 English users, Filipino research writers across disciplines also frequently utilize NNPs in writing academic research (Hernandez, 2021). Specifically, noun premodifiers which are standard features of academic writing (Biber & Gray, 2016) assist Filipino research writers to communicate ideas concisely and efficiently; however, Filipino research writers' use of noun premodifiers is overlooked in academic writing research. This gap hints that noun premodifiers are insufficiently investigated compressed and implicit structures in academic research writing specifically in the Philippines.

Exploring NNPs in disciplinary research articles is important to broaden and deepen L2 English academic writing students' and professionals' knowledge about academic research writing. In the same way, it could offer pedagogical and professional insights into the enhancement of research writing curricula, academic research writing instruction, and academic research journals in the Philippines and other nations where English functions as an L2. Therefore, this paper cross-investigates NNPs in research articles authored by Filipino research writers across Applied Linguistics (AL), Communication (COM), and Measurement and Evaluation (ME).

2. Background

Of all languages, English plays a vital role in the global practices of academic text production (Lillis & Curry, 2010) and is thus considered as the language of research (Flowerdew, 2013; Hernandez, 2022; Lillis & Curry, 2016). Regardless of geographical contexts, English is used by L1 or L2 English research writers (Hernandez, 2022) as the language is possessed by all people who use it (Kachru, 1997). Flowerdew (2013) and Lillis and Curry (2010)

elucidate that 95% of research in natural sciences and 90% of that in social sciences (archived in International Scientific Indexing) are written in English, and 67% of research (indexed in Ulrich's Periodicals Directory) is published in English.

With these figures, English is clearly the common language used in academic publications (Hernandez, 2022); it aids researchers, academic disciplines, and nations in developing scientific production and in creating new academic knowledge across discourse communities (Flowerdew, 2013; Lillis & Curry, 2016; Menghini, 2017; Paltridge, 2013). In general, English is an obligatory language for writing academic research in countries where English is used as an L2. A case in point is the Philippines where English is considered as an institutional language in scholarly writing and academic publication (Dayag, 2012, 2014). Filipino research writers use English in writing and publishing academic research across disciplines. For example, Philippine higher academic institutions demand that students at graduate and undergraduate levels write research in English, so they could obtain academic units and earn their degrees (Hernandez, 2022). Likewise, Philippine research journals in education science, humanities, and social science disciplines require researchers to employ English in writing research articles, research reports, and review articles, so their works could be more accessible and understandable across the world (Hernandez, 2021, 2022).

As a universal register in disciplinary communities, academic writing "takes place all around the world" (Lillis & Curry, 2010, p. 1) and is the key to the spreading of scientific knowledge in academic fields (Gray, 2015). It has different sub-registers like concept and position papers, dissertations, research articles, and theses (Hernandez, 2022). Of these sub-registers, the research article (RA)—aside from the dissertation and thesis as research-based academic texts—represent academic research writing (Biber & Gray, 2010, 2011; Biber et al., 2016; Gray, 2015), which differs from general writing. Researchers (e.g., Biber & Gray, 2016; Gray, 2015; Hyland, 2006) have claimed that language use in academic research writing differs across disciplines, which is supported by the notion that linguistic variation exists across academic discourses. In other words, linguistic features vary in academic written texts based on disciplines, and academic disciplines employ linguistic resources in different manners (Gray, 2015; Hyland, 2006). As disciplines hold various writing practices and knowledge constructions, among others, languages used by discourse communities across disciplines are disparate (Gray, 2015; Hyland, 2007)—called as "situated characteristic" (Flowerdew, 2013, p. 307). In their respective fields, writers also carefully use linguistic resources according to writing conventions or standards (Biber, 2006; Hyland & Tse, 2005; Salmani Nodoushan, 2023b). However, this view of linguistic differences across

disciplines is barely extended to L2 academic research writing in the Philippines (Hernandez, 2022).

Of the sub-registers of academic research writing, the RA has earned the utmost recognition because of the important role it plays in the dissemination of research results among scientific discourse communities (Flowerdew, 1999; Swales, 2004). Research articles (RAs) are scholarly written texts which present systematically-produced content, knowledge, or perspective (van Enk & Power, 2017). Relative to this definition, the RA has sub-classifications based on the research paradigms in the hard disciplines (i.e., physical and natural sciences which deal with the scientific method and empirical results) and soft disciplines (i.e., behavioral sciences, humanities, and social sciences which focus on the systematic analysis of human behaviors or cognitions, and texts) (Gray, 2015). Gray (2015) sub-categorizes RAs into qualitative, quantitative, and theoretical RA sub-registers, which are applicable in various academic disciplines (Hernandez, 2022). Qualitative RAs use qualitative research designs and instruments (e.g., ethnography, focus group discussion, etc.) usually in soft disciplines like Applied Linguistics, Education, etc. Quantitative RAs employ quantitative research designs (e.g., experimental, survey, etc.) normally in hard disciplines like Chemistry, Engineering, etc. Theoretical RAs discuss approaches or theories in soft disciplines such as Philosophy, Political Science, etc. Gray (2015) claims that NNPs are distinguishing syntactic resources of theoretical, qualitative, and quantitative disciplinary RAs.

Making academic research writing syntactically complex at the phrasal level, NNPs are one of the most common nominal modifiers. However, they are scarcely explored in L2 academic research writing particularly in the Philippines. Current studies (e.g., Biber & Gray, 2010, 2011, 2016; Biber et al., 2016; Biber et al., 1999, 2021; Gray, 2015; Hernandez, 2021; Hutter, 2015; Ruan, 2018; Wu et al., 2020) have concentrated on syntactic complexity features but did not emphasize NNPs alone. For example, Hernandez (2021) revealed that noun premodifiers ranked as the third phrasal modifiers characterizing education science, humanities, and social science RAs written by Filipino researchers. Similarly, Ruan (2018) reported that nouns as premodifiers, aside from attributive adjectives and nominal prepositional phrases, were most commonly employed in applied linguistics RA abstracts written by Chinese as L2 English research writers and L1 English research writers. In addition, Wu et al. (2020) discovered that complex nominal phrases including noun premodifiers were greatly used in humanities, science, and social science ELF RAs. While these studies concentrated on L2 academic research writing, Biber and Gray (2010, 2011, 2016), Biber et al. (2016), Biber et al. (1999, 2021), and Hutter (2015) focused on L1 academic research writing. They showed that NNPs were one of the principal compressed and implicit syntactic features of RAs across soft and hard disciplines.

These related studies show that academic research writing tolerates compact information packaging and implicit meaning relations. However, only Hernandez (2021) considered L2 academic research writing by Filipino researchers, and none of the related studies have cross-investigated NNPs in disciplinary RAs authored by Filipino research writers. Hence, noun premodifiers are under-researched compressed and implicit syntactic structures in disciplinary RAs in the Philippines.

Cross-analyzing NNPs in qualitative (QUAL) and quantitative (QUAN) disciplinary RAs authored by Filipino research writers is important for the following grounds: First, they are nominal modifiers used by Filipino research writers across disciplines in writing RAs (Hernandez, 2021); thus, their use of NNPs merits investigation; second, English is an institutional language in scholarly writing and research publications in the Philippines (Dayag, 2012, 2014); hence, English noun premodifiers used by Filipino research writers deserve examination; third, noun premodifiers are syntactic features of academic research writing (Biber & Gray, 2010, 2011, 2016; Biber et al., 1999, 2016, 2021; Gray, 2015; Hernandez, 2021; Hutter, 2015; Lu et al., 2021; Ruan, 2018; Wu et al., 2020), but they are unfortunately underexplored in L2 academic writing research in the Philippines; and fourth, no research has been done, cross-investigating noun premodifiers in QUAL and QUAN disciplinary RAs written by Filipino research writers. These reasons strongly indicate that initiating research on NNPs in L2 academic research writing in the Philippines is a dire need.

In this study, I cross-examine NNPs in published research articles authored by Filipino research writers (FRWs) across QUAL and QUAN AL RAs, QUAL and QUAN COM RAs, and QUAN ME RAs. Specifically, I have sought (1) to determine the frequencies of use of noun premodifiers in QUAL and QUAN disciplinary RAs and (2) to identify whether these noun premodifiers significantly differ across disciplines.

3. Method

3.1. Framework

I employed Biber et al.'s (2021, pp. 585-586) NNPs framework (Table 1), with the aid of Hernandez's (2021) syntactic patterns. NNPs usually consist of two parts: the noun premodifier and the head noun. Each NNP represents two contradicting extremes of communicative aims: (1) they cause "extremely dense packaging of referential information" (Biber et al., 2021, p. 584) or compression of syntactic structure, and (2) they create "extreme reliance on implicit meaning" (Biber et al., 2021, p. 584). Although they aid academic research writers to express information in as few words as possible, NNPs urge

readers to infer the intended meaning relations between the noun premodifier and the head noun (Biber et al., 1999, 2021).

Table 1
NNPs Framework

NNPs	Elaborated or compressed syntactic alternatives
1 law report	report <i>about law</i> [COMPRESSED]
2 heart attack	attack <i>in the heart</i> [COMPRESSED]
3 glass bottle	bottle <u>that is made of glass</u> [ELABORATED]
4 asphalt rooftop	rooftop <u>that uses asphalt</u> [ELABORATED]
5 family affair	affair <i>in the family</i> [COMPRESSED]

The concealed meaning relations between the premodifying noun and the head noun could be uncovered by their explicit or less implicit syntactic equivalents (Biber & Gray, 2010, 2016; Biber et al., 1999, 2021). For instance, *law report*, *heart attack*, and *family affair* (see Table 1) have corresponding alternatives—‘report about law’, ‘attack in the heart’, and ‘affair in the family’—which are all prepositional phrases as noun postmodifiers (i.e., compressed and less implicit syntactic alternatives); *glass bottle* and *asphalt rooftop* have ‘bottle that is made of glass’ and ‘rooftop that uses asphalt’ as their respective relative clauses (i.e., elaborated and explicit syntactic alternatives).

By syntactic pattern, each NNP is a single ‘noun as noun premodifier’, following noun + noun sequence. Hernandez (2021) explains that single NNPs are structured as N + N (or PN + HN) where the first N is the premodifying noun (PN) and the underlined N is the head noun (HN). However, complex noun + noun sequences could be N + N + N or N + N + N + . . . + N (Hernandez, 2021). On the one hand, N + N + N contains two or double NNPs (the first and the second Ns) before the head noun (the third N). On the other hand, N + N + N + . . . + N contains three or more NNPs (the first, the second, and the third Ns as premodifying Ns). The ellipsis points (. . .) after the third noun premodifier mean that more subsequent nouns may occur to premodify the head noun (the last N).

3.2. Procedure

Register analysis was used as the discourse approach to cross-analyze NNPs in the QUAL and QUAN sub-registers of disciplinary RAs. Data sources were 42 randomly picked RAs, published in Open Access (OA) Philippine research journals and authored by FRWs in AL, COM, and ME. RAs were chosen because they embody academic research writing (Biber & Gray, 2016; Gray, 2015; Swales, 2004). OA Philippine research journals were considered to represent L2 academic research writing performance of FRWs across the Philippines. The three disciplines—AL, COM, and ME—were selected because they are growing

research fields in the Philippines. AL and ME are sub-fields of social sciences while COM is a sub-discipline of humanities. The disciplinary RAs were collected from a period of 10 years because this study is a synchronic investigation. Table 2 shows the description of the selected disciplinary RAs.

Table 2

Description of Selected Disciplinary RA Sub-Registers

Years	Type	Discipline	No. of RAs	Tokens
2010-2018	QUAL	AL	7	27,189
2009-2019		COM	7	31,470
2011-2019		ME	-	-
2010-2018	QUAN	AL	7	30,088
2009-2019		COM	7	33,100
2011-2019		ME	14	55,889
Total		3	42	177,736

The 42 RAs consisted of 14 RAs per discipline—overall 177,736 tokens—to meet the equivalent number of texts (Hernandez, 2022). Based on Gray's (2015) QUAL and QUAN RA sub-registers, the selected RAs were classified into five RA datasets, namely (1) qualitative AL (AL-QUAL, 7 RAs), (2) quantitative AL (AL-QUAN, 7 RAs), (3) qualitative COM (COM-QUAL, 7 RAs), and (4) quantitative COM (COM-QUAN, 7 RAs), and (5) quantitative ME (ME-QUAN, 14 RAs). No QUAL RAs were sampled for ME because Philippine OA journals mostly publish QUAN ME RAs that deal with empirical data interpretation (Hernandez, 2021). The five disciplinary RA sub-registers were compared and/or contrasted as different datasets.

For data analysis, I utilized *LancsBox* (Brezina et al., 2021) to automatically analyze NNPs in QUAL and QUAN RA sub-registers. The automatic analyses generated by the corpus tool were saved in Excel documents. On Excel files, I performed a manual analysis of all cases of noun premodifiers in each disciplinary RA sub-register. Doing hand-coding was essential because corpus tools may also yield inconsistent results (Egbert et al., 2020). Three qualified external coders independently cross-examined all the noun premodifiers, which I had coded. Two inter-coding rounds emerged. In the first, each coder and I met and found contrasting decisions. We conducted further discussions until we arrived at similar judgments. In the second, each coder and I met again after several days to reassess our judgments until we reached a final decision. Inter-coder reliability using Fleiss Kappa was estimated at 0.98 (an almost perfect reliability agreement).

To make the frequencies of use of NNPs directly comparable, I normalized each raw frequency count of noun premodifiers by the total number of words of

each QUAL and QUAN disciplinary RA sub-register. Then, I multiplied each raw count by 1,000 words (as norming number), following relevant corpus-based studies (e.g., Biber, 1988; Biber & Gray, 2016; Gray, 2015). Afterwards, I divided each normalized frequency rate to the total number of words of each disciplinary RA sub-register to compute for the equivalent percentages (Cheusheva, 2021). One-way ANOVA between groups was also employed to determine if there was a significant difference in the frequencies of use of noun premodifiers between and among disciplinary RAs.

4. Results

This section presents the findings and their interpretations. Results are compared and/or contrasted with the past studies wherever appropriate.

Figure 1.

Distributions of NNPs

Overall, NNPs were extremely frequent across the five disciplinary RA sub-registers (Figure 1). They occurred most frequently in ME-QUAN RAs (58.44, 5.84%); however, they almost equally co-occurred in AL-QUAN RAs (49.36, 4.94%), COM-QUAN RAs (48.76, 4.88%), and COM-QUAL RAs (48.11, 4.81%). They were least common in AL-QUAL RAs (40.05, 4.01%). The leading of noun premodifiers in ME-QUAN RAs followed by AL-QUAN RAs corroborates Biber and Gray's (2016) finding that noun premodifiers are relatively frequent in social science research writing like ME and AL research writing. However, the high frequencies of noun premodifiers in COM-QUAL, COM-QUAN, and AL-QUAL RAs also contradict Biber and Gray's (2016) results. They reported that noun premodifiers are occasional in humanities research writing like COM

research writing, but they are comparatively common in social science research writing like AL research writing.

These disparities could be explained by the fact that Biber and Gray's (2016) study involved disciplinary RAs as a single sub-register of academic research writing whereas the current study divided disciplinary RAs into QUAL and QUAN RA sub-registers. Despite these, the findings suggest that FRWs most commonly employ NNPs in writing ME-QUAN research. In addition, they relatively frequently use them in writing AL-QUAN, COM-QUAN, and COM-QUAL research. However, they less commonly employ them in writing AL-QUAL research. Overall, the differing frequencies of use of noun premodifiers across the five disciplinary RA sub-registers resonate Gray's (2015) claim that language use differs within sub-registers of disciplinary RAs.

To determine whether NNPs significantly differ in frequencies of use across disciplinary RAs, one-way ANOVA between groups was run. Results showed that NNPs were not significantly different at the $p < .05$ level [$F(2,3) = 3.34, p = < .17$], indicating that there exists no significant difference in the frequencies of use of noun premodifiers across disciplinary RAs. Post hoc Tukey *HSD* test yielded that the mean scores between disciplinary RAs were not significantly different: AL RAs ($M = 44.71, SD = 6.58$) and COM RAs ($M = 48.44, SD = 0.46$); AL RAs ($M = 44.71, SD = 6.58$) and ME RAs ($M = 29.22, SD = 11.96$); and COM RAs ($M = 48.44, SD = 0.46$) and ME RAs ($M = 29.22, SD = 11.96$). These findings strongly show that NNPs are widely and consistently used in the three disciplinary RAs. Thus, it can be construed that they contribute to the syntactic compression and semantic implicitness of RAs across the three disciplines.

As NNPs were most recurrent in ME-QUAN RAs, these compressed and implicit syntactic features probably recur in every sentence in ME-QUAN RAs. This is illustrated in samples 1 to 3 from ME-QUAN RAs, with NNPs (bolded) and their head nouns (underlined).

- (1) **Document** analysis was done to survey the **research** priorities of the **state** universities involved. [ME-QUAN]
- (2) In a **state** university, in the Philippines, a **quality** assurance initiative through **learning** assessment was undertaken. [ME-QUAN]
- (3) The whole **achievement goal orientation** scale was able to obtain an alpha of .87, while whole **procrastination** scale obtained an alpha of .86 and the whole **perfectionism** scale had an alpha of .80, which are all good indicators of scale internal consistency. [ME-QUAN]

QUAN RA, 6 from a COM-QUAN RA, and 8 from an AL-QUAL RA have corresponding nominal *of-* or *about-*phrase alternatives—‘instruction of reading skills’, ‘satisfaction about communication’, and ‘community of (spoken) discourse’. While the equivalent relative *that*-clauses make the logical relation between the single noun premodifiers and the head nouns explicit, the alternative nominal prepositional phrases make a balance between compression and explicitness (Biber & Gray, 2010, 2016; Wu et al., 2020).

In the following sections, noun premodifiers are shown to co-occur in double and multiple noun sequences. Double and multiple noun sequences were not given emphasis in Biber et al.’s (1999, 2021) study. These noun sequences have even more complicated meaning relations not only because of the lack of syntactic constituents but also because of more than one embedded noun premodifiers, causing more confusing meaning relations.

4.2. Double NNPs

Double NNPs are patterned as N + N + N (Hernandez, 2021). Unlike single noun premodifiers, double noun premodifiers have more complicated meaning relations in the sense that the first noun premodifier refers to the second noun premodifier, and the second noun premodifier refers to the head noun, or each of the noun premodifiers pertains to the head noun (Ruan, 2018). Their unclear meaning relations could also be made explicit by their elaborated syntactic alternatives and less implicit by their compressed syntactic equivalents. Consider the following double noun premodifiers from the disciplinary RA sub-registers, with their *that-* or *who-*clause alternatives (underlined) and nominal prepositional phrase equivalents (italicized).

(9) research training program [ME-QUAN] → program that trains participants about research

N + N + N

or research training program

(10) teacher efficacy model [AL-QUAN] → model *of the efficacy of teachers*

N + N + N

or teacher efficacy model

 (11) mass media use [COM-QUAN] → use of *media for the masses*
 N + N + N

 or mass media use

 (12) media placement contract [COM-QUAL] → contract of *the placement of media*
 N + N + N

 or media placement contract

 (13) Adult language learning [AL-QUAL] → adults who are learning language
 N + N + N

 or adult language learning

These double NNPs illustrate vague meaning associations, as signaled by curved down arrows. Example 9 from an ME-QUAN RA has the first noun premodifier 'research', premodifying the second noun premodifier 'training' which premodifies the head noun 'program', or it may be the case that each noun premodifier ('research' and 'training') separately refers to the head noun 'program'. These two different meaning relations could be clarified by the relative *that*-clause—'program that trains participants about research'. The same ambiguous meaning associations could be seen in example 13 from an AL-QUAL RA, which could be made explicit by the *who*-clause—'adults who are learning language'. Unlike 9 and 13, examples 10 from an AL-QUAN RA, 11 from a COM-QUAN RA, and 12 from a COM-QUAL RA have the corresponding 'model of the efficacy of teachers', 'use of media for the masses', and 'contract of the placement of media' as their nominal prepositional phrase alternatives. As

these alternatives originated from double noun premodifiers, they tend to contain two embedded prepositional phrases, as shown in the following:

model →
 of the efficacy →
 of teachers

use →
 of media →
 for the masses

contract →
 of the placement →
 of media

These embedded prepositional phrase equivalents signpost that the disciplinary RA sub-registers consistently reflect the compressed and implicit written discourse style of academic research writing. Since prepositional phrases as noun postmodifiers are variants of NNPs (Biber & Gray, 2016), noun premodifiers in the disciplinary RA sub-registers are inflexible syntactic structures in that they usually have nominal prepositional phrase counterparts. Multiple noun premodifiers can co-occur consecutively before the head noun, as discussed in the next section.

4.3. Multiple NNPs

Multiple NNPs are syntactically structured as N + N + N + . . . + N (Hernandez, 2021), depicting a much more complex structural pattern. Multiple noun premodifiers create much more baffling logical relationships with the head nouns. As with most single and double noun premodifiers above, meaning relations in multiple noun premodifiers could be uncovered by nominal prepositional phrases. Consider the following multiple noun premodifiers from the disciplinary RA sub-registers, with multiple embedded nominal prepositional phrases as their compressed and less explicit syntactic alternatives.

(14) Student Confidence Level Result [ME-QUAN] → *level of the result of the confidence test of students*

N + N + N + N

or Student Confidence Level Result

 (15) English language proficiency level [AL-QUAN] → *level of the proficiency in the English language*

 N + N + N + N

 or English language proficiency level

 (16) SMOG readability test index [COM-QUAN] → *index of SMOG test for the readability of text*

 N + N + N + N

 or SMOG readability test index

 (17) Rainbow Rights Project Media Reference Guide [COM-QUAL] → *Reference guide on the project media of Rainbow Rights*

 N + N + N + N + N + N

 or Rainbow Rights Project Media Reference Guide

 (18) reading literacy scale score [AL-QUAL] → *score on the scale of literacy in reading*

 N + N + N + N

 or reading literacy scale score

These nominal prepositional phrases form exactly like noun premodifiers and attributive adjectives, which are all embedded noun phrase structures (Biber & Gray, 2016). Like noun premodifiers and attributive adjectives, they foster very dense packaging of information (Biber et al. 1999, 2021; Biber & Gray, 2010, 2016; Ruan, 2018). Thus, the strings of embedded prepositional phrases above strongly indicate that the disciplinary RA sub-registers rely heavily on the use of dependent nominal premodifiers and are characterized with compressed and implicit written discourse style. Likewise, FRWs in ME, AL, and COM frequently employ and maintain this discourse style in writing QUAN and QUAL research regardless of disciplines.

5. Conclusion

With the existing scarcity of research on NNPs in L2 academic research writing by L2 English users, I cross-investigated noun premodifiers in AL, COM, and ME RAs written by FRWs. Accordingly, NNPs were dominantly used across disciplinary RA sub-registers, particularly in ME-QUAN RAs with the greatest frequency of use of noun premodifiers. As revealed by one-way ANOVA between groups with Post hoc Tukey *HSD*, NNPs did not differ significantly across disciplinary RAs. In conclusion, NNPs are universal and significant, compressed and implicit syntactic features of QUAN and QUAL RAs across the three disciplines. FRWs frequently employ these noun premodifiers in AL, COM, and ME RAs to convey information in the least possible words and thus sustain solidly dense packaging of information in writing QUAN and QUAL research.

In addition, noun premodifiers make QUAN and QUAL RAs specialized sub-registers of academic research writing irrespective of disciplines. In his study, Hernandez (2022) avers that *of*-phrases as the characteristic nominal prepositional phrases in QUAN and QUAL Curriculum and Instruction, Psychology, and Sociology RAs have 'applied' implications for research writing curricula and academic research writing instruction and so concludes this study. Aside from these, the study also has benefits for academic research journals in contexts where English is used as an L2.

On academic research writing curricula, research writing curriculum developers in AL, COM, and ME may consult with applied linguists or academic writing specialists in incorporating NNPs as language foci in the academic research curricula. Hernandez (2021) notes that research writing curricula in the Philippines have paucity of the integration of the related compressed and implicit syntactic features in writing disciplinary research; he adds that this dearth generates challenges for graduate professionals and undergraduate students in writing QUAN and QUAL research (Hernandez, 2022). By coalescing NNPs into the research curricula, professionals and students can be

notified of noun premodifiers as expected compressed and implicit syntactic features to employ in writing disciplinary research regardless of research designs.

On academic research writing instruction, teachers ought to provide extensive writing practice and exercises on single, double, and multiple noun premodifiers for students to develop their discourse style in writing QUAN and QUAL research. Besides syntactic patterns, writing practice and exercises should also involve paraphrasing activities to unfold the equivalent elaborated structures and intended explicit meanings of noun premodifiers (see Salmani Nodoushan, 2021a, 2022 for more on ‘meaning’ and ‘intentionality’). As a ‘washback’ effect (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021c) of the current study, students could be trained on figuring out the accurate meaning relations between noun premodifiers and the head nouns. Samples of noun premodifiers should be selected from a corpus of QUAN and QUAL disciplinary RAs authored by FRWs, and academic research writing instructional resources should be written by Filipino academic writing teachers (Hernandez, 2020, 2021). Hence, these could help graduate and undergraduate students in the three disciplines to enhance their syntactic skills in writing academic research and could make academic research writing courses more contextualized (Hernandez, 2022).

On academic research journals, research publishers in the three disciplines should specify NNPs as one of the linguistic requirements in the author/submission guidelines. By doing so, potential research authors can be informed about the particular syntactic features which editors-in-chief and peer reviewers expect when evaluating submitted research manuscripts. Moreover, researchers across the three disciplines may produce well-written RAs, reflective of the nominal discourse style of L2 academic research writing.

All in all, this study—which might somehow be considered an action research (Salmani Nodoushan, 2023a)—has charted a cross-investigation of NNPs in L2 academic writing research in the Philippines and in contexts where English is used as an L2. However, it recommends trajectories for future research. First, comparing and contrasting noun premodifiers in astronomy, biology, and physics RAs with law, philosophy, and political science RAs could report more similarities and differences between the hard and soft disciplines. Second, cross-examining disciplinary RAs written by other L2 English research writers across the world may unveil the similar and different ways they utilize noun premodifiers in their own research communities. In addition, exploring noun premodifiers in disciplinary RAs vis-à-vis disciplinary research presentations could provide more valuable insights for students and professionals on the syntactic features to use when writing research for publication and presenting papers in conferences. Moreover, re-examining noun premodifiers in a larger corpus of disciplinary RAs is necessary for generating stronger generalizations.

These research directions could offer more valuable implications for research writing curricula, academic research writing instruction, and academic research journals. They may even enhance professional courses on academic research for publication. NNPs are often underexplored compressed and implicit syntactic features of L2 academic research writing especially in the Philippines; therefore, further cross-investigations of noun premodifiers in disciplinary published RAs written by L2 English research writers are imperative.

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